

GENDER INEQUALITY ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS AND CHANGING PERSPECTIVES OF PEOPLE

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1.Introduction :

Even in this era of modernization and development, there are still doubts in the societal perspectives with regards to roles and responsibilities of gender. Gender Equality in a short line is equality among all types of gender in society in terms of each gender rights. It means that every citizen of any country or society must be given equal rights for survival in society. Even though the society is changing and evolving, even though there have been various reforms and efforts being taken with respect to gender equalization, there are still some examples prevalent in the society such as Glass Ceiling culture practiced in the corporal sectors, a man if seen crying is considered weak or effeminate. The stereotypical roles that women are weaker sections of society and men class considered to have an upper edge are divided to such extent and are so deep rooted that even though the efforts are taken for gender equality, still the society finds it difficult to accept the changing roles of genders and that gender inequality is still a major concern to be pondered upon. Even though Women are giving an equal edge to men in almost all the fields from IT to Sports, right from Chanda Koccher to Mary Kom to Kumud Shrinivasan to Saina Nehwal to Mary Kom , the capabilities are still questioned. Why can't the man of the house cook dinner for his family? Why can't a female be the bread winner and the decision maker of her family? Why can't Men cry and vent out their emotions? Why a women is always steoreotyped to be weak and tender and on the other hand males as strong and demanding? This kind of deep rooted stereotypical gender role nurturing has lead to various crimes towards women such as rapes, dowry deaths, physical and mental abuse and the counting goes on. There is still an alarming need towards gender equality for a mutual co-existence for each gender.

2.Theoretical Background:Inequality in gender and how gender equality is seen nowadays

The word gender describes the socially-constructed roles and responsibilities that societies consider appropriate for men and women. Gender equality means that men and women have equal power and equal opportunities for financial independence, education, and personal development . Guaranteeing the rights of women and giving them opportunities to reach their full potential is critical not only for attaining gender equality, but also for meeting a wide range of international development goals. Empowered women and girls contribute to the health and productivity of their families, communities, and countries, creating a ripple effect that benefits everyone However, Globally, women have fewer opportunities for economic participation than men, less access to basic and higher education, greater health and safety risks, and less political representation nowadays gender equality has gaining its importance has many of the women has broke the glass barriers set by the society and has proven themselves competent still there are various confusions and perplexing views in the minds of the people .this research is hence done to check how accepting we are in accepting this concept of gender equality for a better society.

3.Methodology:

The data was collected from 50 student teachers and also students from junior colleges through a survey .the data was analysed qualitatively using coding method.

The questions asked were :

1. Do you think women are fully heard?
2. Which place do you think voice of women is unheard?
3. Have you faced any gender inequality?
4. Are you a believer of traditional gender roles?
5. Can female be the man of the house?
6. Do you think women can replace men in areas professionally managed by of male dominance?

4. Research Findings

The research findings are presented according to the aforementioned research questions. Distribution of the answer is also based on the respondents.

Q.1. Do you think women are fully heard?

6. Do you think women are fully heard?

Yes	15.38%	6
No	79.49%	31
Other (please specify)	5.13%	2

79.49% of the individual believe that the voice of women is unheard or not fully heard whereas 15.38% individual believe that its fully heard while others specified that it is partially heard due to lesser availability of platforms for women to come out and speak.

Q.2. Which place do you think voice of women is unheard?

7. Which places do you think women's voice is unheard?

Home	10.26%	4
Work	12.82%	5
Decision making process	69.23%	27
Other (please specify)	7.69%	3

69.23% of individuals believe that voice of women is went unheard in the decision making process. 12.82% believe that voice of women at work is waived off, 10.26% believe that opinions of women at home are unheard and others state that in all the above fields at some point or other the voice of women is unheard.

Q.3. Have you faced any gender inequality?

10. Have you faced or experienced any gender inequality?

Yes	58.97%	23
No	38.46%	15
Other (please specify)	2.56%	1

58.97% individuals believe that they have experienced gender inequality while 38.46% agree that they have not faced any gender inequality while other 2.56% stated that they have not experienced it but noticed it in their society.

Q.6. Are you a believer of traditional gender roles?

Yes	22.86%	8
No	74.29%	26
Other (please specify)	2.86%	1

Although 22.5% of the people still believe that men are the breadwinners and women are better in managing household duties , 74% of the respondents s feel that they believe that traditional gender roles are not the matter of concern in recent decades has women have equally proved themselves in all the fields of study , other has specified that this thinking of women being the housewife is still prevalent in various areas which has to be reduced .

Q.4. Can female be the Man of the house ?

87% of the respondents have said yes ,that female can be the man of the house , while the response shows changing perspective of people towards gender roles and economic status of women in a growing stage ,3% response still feel that only male can manage household duties more effectively , others have specified that even if a women is competent, the prevalant mindset of people regarding gender roles is being the barrier in allowing a women to achieve this status.

Q.5. Do you think women can replace men in areas professionally managed by male dominance ?

The response show that more than 90% of the respondents feel that women can manage any tasks that is believed to b handled effectively by a male , and 6% of the people still feel that depending upon the competency and skill

a women can definitely handle any post with ease not necessary that it can only b a male dominating task and it is also proved by many women has they have achieved great heights in all fields and been successful .

6.Conclusion

From this research, I and my fellow researcher concluded that there are various steps been taken, various opportunities been given in order to take effective steps towards gender equalization but still we have'nt been there. Around 53.85% individuals believe that we have attained equaity with respect to gender roles while 46.15% individuals still state that we still have to attain gender equality. 89.74% individuals still believe that gender stereotypes acts as the barrier in the changing perspective of the society. 87.18% believe that women too can be the man the house, but my question to the society is why a female has to become a man in order to prove her capabilities. In order to get her rights given to her. Why she still can't be the female of the society and still have equality with respect to roles and responsibilities of gender.

Along with the changing era nd needs of today's scenario, its indeed high time to bring about a change in the mindset of the individuals in order to uproot the deep rooted societal barriers of the gender. We as future teachers of the country having the power to mold the citizens of our country should take a oath of ingraining seeds of equality among our students for a better world for each gender tomorrow.